

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE
AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR WITH
THE MEDIATING ROLE OF COMMITMENT AND
IDENTIFICATION**

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Abstract

The objective of the study is to find relationship between organizational justice (OJ) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) with the mediating role of affective commitment (AC) and organizational identification (OI) of the employees working in the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in Bangladesh. A convenient sampling technique was utilized, and a 37-item questionnaire was distributed among 185 NGO employees working in different NGOs located in Dhaka. PLS-SEM 4.1.0 was utilized to test the hypothesized model. Results found that OJ and OCB don't have positive relationships. However, OI and AC sequentially mediate the relationship, indicating the presence of perceived identification enhances AC among employees and which in turn increase the OCB of the staffs.

Keywords: Organizational justice, organizational citizenship behavior, organizational identification, affective commitment, PLS-SEM.

1. Introduction

In the evolving landscape of organizational behavior, the interplay between organizational justice (OJ) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has garnered significant scholarly attention over the years due to their impact on employee performance and organizational effectiveness. OJ refers to employees' perceptions of fairness in the workplace, encompassing distributive, procedural, and interactional fairness (Saufi, 2024). On the other hand, OCB encompasses discretionary employee behaviors that go beyond formal job requirements and contribute positively to organizational functioning (Organ, 1988; Ndoja & Malekar, 2020). As noted by Organ, OCB is shaped by various factors, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work-life balance, quality of work-life, leadership, and motivation, among others (Titisari, 2014). The research also found that OCB positively impacts organizational output, efficiency, cost cut, and customer happiness (Podsakoff et al., 2009; Yildiz & Amin, 2020). Understanding the nexus between these two constructs

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is crucial, particularly in contexts where employee engagement and discretionary effort are vital for achieving organizational goals.

A mounting body of investigation highlights that the link of OJ and OCB is not straightforward but is mediated by various psychological and emotional factors, such as affective commitment (AC) and organizational identification (OI). AC refers to the emotional attachment and identification employees feel toward their organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Wang et al., 2020). Studies have demonstrated that perceptions of fairness enhance AC, which in turn promotes OCB among employees. For instance, Guh et al. (2013) found that AC mediates the relationship between OJ and OCB, highlighting the importance of emotional bonds in eliciting discretionary work behaviors (Kapil & Rastogi, 2020). OI, on the other hand, pertains to the extent to which employees align their self-concept with the organization's identity (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Pattnaik & Tripathy, 2020). When employees feel they are treated fairly, they are more inclined to align with the organization's values and objectives, which fosters greater involvement in tasks beyond their official job duties (Rahman & Karim, 2022). This identification fosters a sense of belonging and loyalty, motivating employees to contribute to the organization's success through OCB. These mediating factors serve as critical mechanisms through which justice perceptions translate into OCB.

The study of OJ and OCB is particularly essential for non-governmental organizations (NGOs), operating in complex and resource-constrained environments, offering a unique setting for studying these dynamics (Chanase, 2023). NGOs often rely heavily on the commitment and discretionary contributions of their employees to fulfill their missions. Therefore, fostering a perception of justice and leveraging commitment and organizational identification becomes critical for enhancing OCB in such organizations. Despite their importance, the interplay of these constructs within the NGO context remains underexplored. This study seeks to bridge this gap by examining the relationships between OJ, OCB, AC, and OI among employees working in NGOs. By understanding these relationships, the research could provide theoretical insights and practical implications for NGO leaders to foster a culture of fairness, strengthen employee commitment, and encourage behaviors that enhance organizational effectiveness.

1.1 Problem Statement

NGOs play a critical role in Bangladesh's socio-economic development, addressing issues such as poverty alleviation, education, healthcare, and disaster management. The effectiveness of these organizations heavily relies on the commitment and discretionary efforts of their employees, (Islam *et al.*, 2021). However, sustaining such behaviors in the non-profit sector is challenging due to resource constraints, high workload, and limited monetary rewards (Rahman & Biswas, 2016). These factors make it essential to explore the determinants of OCB within the context of NGOs in Bangladesh. OJ including distributive, procedural, and interactional justice, has been identified as a key driver of OCB across various sectors (Colquitt et al., 2013). Fair treatment within organizations fosters trust, enhances employee satisfaction, and encourages voluntary behaviors that contribute to organizational effectiveness (Xu *et al.*, 2016). Although OJ is important for fostering OCB, its specific impact within the

unique setting of NGOs in Bangladesh remains largely unexplored, creating a significant gap in the research.

Additionally, AC and OI, two psychological mechanisms that mediate the relationship between organizational justice and OCB, are yet to be thoroughly examined in Bangladesh's NGO sector. Studies have shown that AC is influenced by perceptions of fairness and, in turn, promotes discretionary efforts (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Changaranchola & Samantara, 2024). Similarly, OI, which reflects the alignment of employees' self-concept with organizational values, strengthens when employees perceive fair treatment, leading to increased engagement in OCB (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Nasrin, 2019; Amah & Okesipe 2024). However, empirical evidence on these mediating mechanisms in Bangladesh's NGO sector is scarce. This lack of research is particularly concerning the critical role NGOs play in Bangladesh's development landscape. Thus, to address the above research gaps this study will enquire to what extent OJ is associated with OCB, and whether the mediation effects of OI and AC influence the tie of OJ and OCB, specifically within the context of employees working in NGOs in Bangladesh.

1.2 Research Objectives

This study will focus on examining the relationship between OJ and OCB, considering the mediating role of OI and AC. Therefore, the specific objectives are

- to identify the relationship of OJ, AC, and OI with OCB;
- to evaluate the influence of OI and OJ with AC;
- to investigate the indirect influences of OI, and AC on the link of OJ and OCB;
- to analyze the intervening role of AC in the relationships between OI and OCB, and OJ, OI and OCB.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

OCB describes the voluntary, discretionary actions taken by staff members that go above and beyond the call of duty and enhance the efficiency of the company (Organ, 1988). These behaviors are not explicitly recognized by reward systems but are critical for advancing a collaborative and productive work environment. Examples include helping coworkers, demonstrating initiative, showing loyalty, and endorsing organizational goals. Organ (1997) identified five primary elements of OCB, namely i. altruism, willingly assisting coworkers with job-related issues ii. conscientiousness, going beyond basic job requirements, such as working extra hours, iii. sportsmanship, asserting a positive position and refraining from complaints, iv. courtesy, preventing conflicts by consulting others and providing timely information, and v. civic virtue, actively participating in organizational governance and demonstrating concern for the organization.

Additionally, various factors have been identified as antecedents of OCB, categorized into individual, organizational, and contextual factors. Employees with traits like conscientiousness, agreeableness, and emotional stability are more prone to employ in OCB (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2000; Szostek, 2021). Then, employees with higher emotional

intelligence demonstrate stronger interpersonal behaviors that contribute to OCB (Goleman, 1998). Also, positive attitudes toward work foster a greater likelihood of engaging in OCB (Organ & Ryan, 1995; Chandra et al., 2024). Similarly, there is a constant correlation between higher OCB and organizational elements such as distributive, procedural, and interactional justice, which are all aspects of fair treatment in the workplace (Colquitt et al., 2013).

2.2 Organizational Justice (OJ), Affective Commitment (AC) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

OJ and AC are considered key antecedents of OCB. Workers who believe that their company treats them fairly are more likely to participate in OCB as a way of giving back for the fair treatment they receive (Moorman, 1991; Bizri & Hamieh, 2020). Similarly, AC strengthens employees' willingness to go above and beyond their formal job responsibilities, as they feel emotionally invested in the organization's success (Meyer et al., 2002). Study has consistently demonstrated a positive association of OJ, AC, and OCB, highlighting the interconnected nature of these constructs (Rego & Cunha, 2008).

OJ significantly impacts employees' attitudes and behaviors, fostering trust, satisfaction, and motivation. Workers are more inclined to participate in constructive behaviors, such as OCB, as a kind of reciprocation when they believe that their company is fair (Colquitt et al., 2001; Kyei-Poku, 2024). According to the social exchange theory, which offers a theoretical foundation for comprehending this interaction, workers who believe that justice is being treated fairly are more willing to reciprocate by acting outside of their roles (Blau, 1964). Employees who believe they are being treated properly are more likely to reciprocate by acting in ways that are advantageous to the company, according to research (Organ, 1988; Bala et al., 2022). Moreover, fair treatment fosters trust, satisfaction, and commitment, which are essential for sustaining long-term positive outcomes in organizations (Greenberg, 1990; Bilderback, 2024).

AC is defined as the emotional attachment, identification, and involvement an employee has with their organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991). It reflects the extent to which employees feel a sense of belonging and alignment with the organization's values and goals. Studies have indicated that AC has a substantial impact on workers' inclination to participate in activities beyond official job specifications, including OCB (Riketta, 2005; Ribeiro, 2022).

Additionally, OJ is essential to the development of AC. Workers are more likely to form a close emotional connection with their company if they believe that resources are allocated fairly, decisions are made fairly, and interpersonal interactions are fair (Colquitt et al., 2001; Bankins et al., 2022). Employees are then inspired to take on optional actions that support the growth of the company by this emotional connection (Meyer et al., 2002). Research has also demonstrated how AC mediates the link between OCB and OJ, underscoring its significance in comprehending employee behavior (Rhoades et al., 2001).

Existing literature provides a robust theoretical foundation for understanding the nexus between OJ, AC, and OCB. Studies suggest that OJ positively influences OCB both directly and indirectly through AC. Employees who perceive fairness are more likely to develop an emotional attachment to the organization, which, in turn, motivates them to engage in discretionary behaviors (Colquitt et al., 2001; Rhoades *et al.*, 2001; and O'Connor, & Crowley-Henry, 2019). Given this theoretical framework, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H₁: Organizational justice positively affects organizational citizenship behavior.

H₂: Organizational justice positively influences affective commitment.

H₃: Affective commitment positively affects organizational citizenship behavior.

H₄: Affective commitment mediates the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior.

2.3 Organizational Identification (OI), Affective Commitment (AC) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

OI is the extent to which workers believe they belong and that their identity and that of the company are in harmony (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Weisman et al., 2023). Employees with high OI feel a sense of loyalty and intrinsic drive because they see the objectives, values, and accomplishments of their company as their own. This identification often leads to behaviors that support the organization beyond formal role requirements, referred to as OCB (Van Dick et al., 2006; Sidorenkov et al., 2023).

Research has repeatedly demonstrated that OI and OCB are positively correlated. Strong organizational identification increases the likelihood that workers would act philanthropically, diligently, and cooperatively since they have a personal interest in the company's success (Riketta, 2005; Zulfiqar & Khan, 2021). The fundamental process stems from social identification theory, which holds that people are more likely to support the welfare of a group when they identify with it (in this case, the organization) (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). Additionally, organizational identification strengthens employees' emotional tenderness to the workplace, further motivating them to go beyond official duties to influence to organizational objectives (Dutton et al., 1994; Miao et al., 2019).

AC, defined as the emotional attachment and identification with the organization, is closely related to OI but represents a distinct construct (Meyer & Allen, 1991). While OI focuses on the cognitive alignment between the employee and the organization, AC captures the emotional bond that employees develop as a result of this alignment.

Studies have shown that the link between OI and OCB is mediated by AC. Strong organizational identification frequently results in a strong emotional bond between workers and their company, which in turn motivates them to act in ways that are discretionary (Meyer et al., 2002; Kundi et al., 2023). In other words, OI serves as a cognitive antecedent that fosters AC, which subsequently motivates employees to exhibit OCB (Van Dick et al., 2006). This mediating effect highlights the importance of understanding how emotional and cognitive processes interact to influence employee behavior.

AC has a mediating function in the link between OI and OCB, according to a number of empirical research. For instance, Van Dick et al. (2006) discovered that emotional commitment strongly moderated the association between employees with higher OI and larger OCB. Similarly, Carmeli et al. (2007) highlighted that OI fosters a sense of emotional engagement, which translates into discretionary behaviors that benefit the organization (Langreer, 2024). These findings emphasize the interplay between cognitive and emotional factors in predicting OCB. Based on the theoretical and empirical evidence, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H₅: Organizational identification positively influences organizational citizenship behavior.

H₆: Organizational identification positively influences affective commitment.

H₇: Affective commitment mediates the relationship between organizational identification and organizational citizenship behavior.

2.4 The Relationship between Organizational Justice (OJ), Organizational Identification (OI), Affective Commitment (AC) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

OI is a cognitive connection where employees see themselves as part of their organization, aligning their self-concept with the organization's values and goals (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Bednar *et al.*, 2020). Perceptions of justice play a critical role in fostering OI, as fair treatment enhances employees' trust in the organization and strengthens their sense of belonging (Tyler & Blader, 2003; Helaly & El Shaer, 2021).

Between OJ and OCB, OI serves as a mediator. Employees are more inclined to identify with a company when they believe that its procedures, results, and interactions are fair. Because they see the organization's success as their own, this affiliation encourages people to participate in OCB (Riketta, 2005; Jacobsen & Beehr, 2022). Empirical studies support this relationship, showing that OJ fosters OI, which, in turn, encourages employees to go beyond formal role requirements and engage in discretionary behaviors (De Cremer & van Knippenberg, 2002; Kapil & Rastogi, 2020).

Between OJ and OCB, OI serves as a mediator. Employees are more inclined to identify with a company when they believe that its procedures, results, and interactions are fair. Because they see the organization's success as their own, this affiliation encourages people to participate in OCB (Meyer & Allen, 1991; O'Connor & Crowley-Henry, 2019). This emotional attachment encourages them to engage in OCB, as they feel personally invested in the organization's success (Meyer *et al.*, 2002; Meria *et al.*, 2024).

AC interacts with OI in addition to mediating the direct connection between OJ and OCB. Fair treatment fosters both cognitive identification and emotional attachment, which together influence employees' willingness to go above and beyond their formal job roles (Rhoades *et al.*, 2001; Götz *et al.*, 2020). For example, employees who experience procedural justice may feel a stronger emotional connection to the organization, which motivates them to contribute discretionary efforts.

The link between OJ and OCB has been found to be mediated by both OI and AC. These mediators operate in a complementary manner, with OI representing the cognitive mechanism and AC representing the emotional mechanism (Carmeli *et al.*, 2007; Petitta *et al.*, 2019). OCB is driven by OJ, which also encourages OI and AC.

There is strong evidence from research that OI and AC have moderating functions. For example, research indicates that OI is strongly predicted by procedural and interactional justice, and that OI in turn affects OCB (De Cremer & van Knippenberg, 2002; Srivastava *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, Rhoades *et al.* (2001) and Kapil & Rastogi (2020) found that AC mediates the relationship between OJ and OCB, highlighting the importance of emotional attachment in fostering discretionary behaviors. Based on literature, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H₈: Organizational justice positively influences organizational identification.

H₉: Organizational identification mediates the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior.

H₁₀: Organizational identification mediates the relationship between affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior.

H₁₁: Organizational identification and affective commitment sequentially mediate the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior.

Figure 1: Proposed Model

3. Methods

3.1 Sampling and Data Collection

The participants in this study are Dhaka-based NGOs' staff. Data was collected using the convenient sampling technique from 185 employees. The study employs convenient sampling strategy because it is the most popular in quantitative research and was used when participants in the target population met criteria that are pertinent to this investigation, such as being readily available, living close by, being available at a specific time, and being willing to participate (Dornyei, 2007). Confidentiality is maintained by not naming the organizations. Employees' willingness to fill out the questionnaire was a determining factor in the data collection, which took place between mid-December and mid-February.

3.2 Instruments

To measure the perceived *organizational justice* (OJ) the nine-item scale of Niehoff and Moorman (1993) was utilized. For measuring *affective commitment* (AC), an eight-item scale of Mayer and Allen (1990) was used. Then to measure the *organizational citizenship behavior* (OCB), an eight-item OCB scale developed by Ehrhart (2004) was operated. Finally, to measure the *organizational identification* (OI), a ten-item scale of Mael and Tetrick (1992) was used.

3.3 Measurement

Using Smart-PLS 4.1 software, the data were then bootstrapped to 500 samples to determine population standard errors and estimations of the sampling distribution's appropriateness, ensuring that the sample data accurately reflects the population (Hair *et al.*, 2014). I employed a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree." According to earlier studies, instruments that used a 5-item Likert scale demonstrated good internal consistency in social science and attitude research projects (Croasmun & Ostrom, 2011).

The partial least squares (PLS) structural equation modeling (SEM) approach was used to do a quantitative analysis of the data. The latent character of the variables, which precludes direct measurement, is another reason the PLS-SEM approach was used (Bartholomew *et al.*, 2011). As a result, indicators derived from accepted theories are used to measure the variables under study. This study focuses on latent variables, including OCB as an endogenous variable, OJ as an exogenous variable, and OI and AC as both endogenous and exogenous variables as well as mediators. The PLS-SEM technique of data analysis is separated into two components: an inner model and an outer model. The study is concentrated on reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, as well as validity testing utilizing factor loading tests and average variance extracted (AVE) at the outer model stage. Data analysis in the inner model stage is concentrated on testing hypotheses, determining coefficients, and multicollinearity.

4. Findings

4.1 Demographic Profile

Table 1: Descriptive data results

Descriptive	Characteristics	Total	Percentage
Sex	Male	79	43%
	Female	106	57%
Age	20-29	76	41%
	30-39	80	43%
	40-49	24	13%
	≥50	05	3%
Educational background	Three-year diploma	06	3%
	Bachelor's	144	78%
	Master's	37	20%

Years of experience	Below 5 years	49	26%
	5-9 years	50	27%
	10-19 years	56	30%
	20-above	30	16%

Source: Compiled by author

4.2 Measurement Model

Based on a minimum factor loading score of 0.7 (Hair Jr et al., 2017; Chin et al., 2003), items are discarded from the constructs. Table 2 shows all the constructs exhibited a notable degree of reliability, as evidenced by its Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values. Based on the results of the Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and AVE it can be said that the constructs are valid and reliable for further analyses.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Construct Items	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
OCB		0.972	0.974	0.856
OCB1	0.939			
OCB2	0.922			
OCB3	0.836			
OCB4	0.963			
OCB5	0.950			
OCB6	0.954			
OCB8	0.907			
AC		0.933	0.936	0.715
AC1	0.855			
AC2	0.892			
AC4	0.886			
AC5	0.772			
AC6	0.768			
AC7	0.884			
AC8	0.854			
OI		0.954	0.957	0.786
OI1	0.877			

OI2	0.831			
OI3	0.908			
OI4	0.869			
OI5	0.905			
OI7	0.885			
OI8	0.926			
OJ		0.939	0.947	0.769
OJ1	0.944			
OJ2	0.874			
OJ3	0.724			
OJ4	0.931			
OJ5	0.875			
OJ6	0.895			

Source: Compiled by author

4.3 Structural Model

Variance inflation factor (VIF), path coefficient, and multicollinearity tests that measure R-squared are indications of structural model tests. OJ, OI, and OC account for 64% of the variation in the OCB variable, according to the results of the r-square tests shown in Table 3. Other unknown factors are responsible for the remaining percentage. The OJ and OI variables account for 60% of the AC variables. Lastly, the OJ variable describes 44% of the variation in the OI variable.

Table 3: R-square results

Variables	R-square
AC	0.636
OCB	0.605
OI	0.434

Source: Compiled by author

The Fornell-Larker Criteria and HTMT were measured to measure the discriminant validity in Table 3. As part of the discriminant validity test, the square root of the AVE was compared to the link of latent variables; the AVE has a stronger correlation value than the other constructs, supporting the threshold (Hair et al., 2014). As a result, there is favorable discriminant validity for the OJ, OI, OCB, and AC constructs. Again, as all HTMT values are smaller than 0.850, the HTMT ratio results offer more proof that the constructs have good discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Outcomes

Fornell-Larcker criterion						Heterotrait-monotrait ratio	
						OCB <-> AC	0.741
	AC	OCB	OI	OJ	AVE	OI <-> AC	0.832
AC	0.846				0.715	OI <-> OCB	0.775
OCB	0.710	0.925			0.856	OJ <-> AC	0.574
OI	0.795	0.750	0.886		0.786	OJ <-> OCB	0.583
OJ	0.573	0.575	0.659	0.877	0.769	OJ <-> OI	0.675

Source: Compiled by author

Multicollinearity testing is performed to ensure that there is no substantial collinearity between the exogenous variables, as shown in Table 4. The findings show that the exogenous variables' VIF values fall below the 5.00 cutoff point (Hair et al., 2017), proving that the examined constructs are not multicollinear.

Table 5: Collinearity results

VIF	
AC -> OCB	2.747
OI -> AC	1.767
OI -> OCB	3.259
OJ -> AC	1.767
OJ -> OCB	1.788
OJ -> OI	1.000

Source: Compiled by author

To assess the connections between the latent variables under study, hypothesis testing was done. To assess the path coefficient values, which are reported in Table 5 and Figure 3 with p values, hypothesis testing was carried out in this study utilizing bootstrapping.

Table 6: Hypotheses testing result

	β	σ	t	p	Hypothesis	Results
OJ -> OCB	0.118	0.061	1.938	0.053	H1	Rejected
OJ -> AC	0.088	0.054	1.616	0.106	H2	Rejected
AC -> OCB	0.293	0.080	3.645	0.000	H3	Supported
OJ -> AC -> OCB	0.026	0.016	1.577	0.115	H4	Rejected
OI -> OCB	0.439	0.093	4.723	0.000	H5	Supported

OI -> AC	0.737	0.065	11.265	0.000	H6	Supported
OI -> AC -> OCB	0.216	0.063	3.421	0.001	H7	Supported
OJ -> OI	0.659	0.030	21.985	0.000	H8	Supported
OJ -> OI -> OCB	0.289	0.059	4.914	0.000	H9	Supported
OJ -> OI -> AC	0.486	0.048	10.109	0.000	H10	Supported
OJ -> OI -> AC -> OCB	0.142	0.044	3.218	0.001	H11	Supported

Source: Compiled by author

Figure 2: Tested Model

5. Discussion

H_1 was not supported by the study's findings, which OJ had no effect on NGO's AC. This stands in contrast to other research that revealed a positive association between OJ and AC in a variety of organizational contexts (Greenberg, 1990; Colquitt et al., 2001). This disparity may be explained by the particular work environment of NGOs, where staff members are frequently motivated by internal incentives and a personal connection to the organization's objective (Meyer & Allen, 1997).

The study refuted hypothesis H_2 , showing that OJ had no discernible impact on NGO employees' AC. This contrasts with other studies that found a positive relationship between OJ and AC across a range of organizational contexts (Colquitt et al., 2001; Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). According to Meyer and Allen (1997) and Kim and Lee (2007), the distinctive features of NGOs, such as workers' intrinsic motivation, personal alignment with the organization's objective, and perceived job meaningfulness may have a greater influence on AC than OJ.

The study's conclusions are consistent with H_3 , showing that AC significantly affects

NGO employees' OCB. This is consistent with another study that found employees who have an emotional attachment to their company are more prone to go outside of the call of duty (Organ, 1997; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). High AC levels increase prosocial behaviors including supporting coworkers, speaking up for the organization, and exhibiting a strong work ethic because they encourage loyalty and a desire to positively impact the company (Podsakoff et al., 2000). According to Kim and Lee (2007), these results emphasize how crucial it is to promote AC in NGOs by employing tactics including improving goal alignment, offering helpful leadership, and cultivating a good corporate culture.

The results of this study refuted H_4 , showing that AC among NGO personnel acts as a mediator factor between OJ and OCB. This finding runs counter to other research that found that OJ and OCB had a positive indirect association through AC in a variety of organizational contexts (Colquitt et al., 2001; Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). The nonprofit sector may have dynamics in which employees' discretionary actions are more heavily influenced by organizational culture, intrinsic motivation, and mission-driven commitment than by views of justice alone (Kim & Lee, 2007; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001).

The study's results, which demonstrate that OI has a major impact on OCB among NGO staff, corroborate H_5 . Previous research has shown that employees who have a strong feeling of belonging to their organization are more inclined to take initiative and act in ways that benefit their teammates and the business (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Riketta, 2005). According to Van Dick et al. (2006), high levels of OI foster a feeling of community and shared purpose, inspiring workers to go above and beyond the call of duty by exhibiting prosocial conduct, advocacy, and collaboration.

H_6 is supported by the study's findings, which show that OI significantly affects NGO employees' AC. This is in line with other studies that indicate employees who have a high feeling of identification with their company form a greater sense of belonging and a deeper emotional relationship, both of which increase their commitment (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Meyer et al., 2006). If employees feel that their own values and the organization's mission align, they are more likely to remain dedicated and invested in their work (Riketta, 2005; Van Knippenberg & Sleebos, 2006).

The results of this study provide credence to H_7 , showing that AC among NGO personnel acts as a mediator factor between OI and OCB. According to earlier studies, workers who have a strong sense of belonging to their company form a stronger emotional bond with it, which increases their propensity to take on optional actions that benefit the company and their coworkers (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Meyer et al., 2006). Because employees with high AC are more likely to exhibit prosocial behaviors, such as supporting organizational goals, helping coworkers, and going above and beyond formal job expectations, affective commitment is a crucial psychological mechanism that strengthens the relationship between OI and OCB (Riketta, 2005; Van Dick et al., 2006).

H_8 is supported by the study's findings, which show that OJ significantly affects NGO employees' OI. According to earlier studies, equitable and open organizational procedures help workers feel like they belong and are part of the company (Tyler & Blader, 2003; Olkkonen & Lipponen, 2006). Employees are more likely to internalize

the organization's values and view themselves as essential members of the team when they believe they are treated fairly in terms of decision-making, resource distribution, and interpersonal treatment (Colquitt et al., 2001; De Cremer & Tyler, 2007).

OJ promotes OCB through the mediating effect of OI among NGO personnel, according to the study's findings, which corroborate H_9 . According to earlier studies, treating employees fairly inside a company increases their sense of identification and belonging, which encourages them to take on optional actions that advance the company (Tyler & Blader, 2003; Olkkonen & Lipponen, 2006). When workers believe that decisions, interactions, and resource distribution are fair, they are more likely to internalize organizational values and demonstrate a stronger commitment to prosocial behaviors like supporting organizational initiatives, helping colleagues, and going above and beyond the call of duty (Colquitt et al., 2001; De Cremer & Tyler, 2007).

H_{10} is supported by the study's findings, which show that OJ mediates emotional AC among NGO personnel through OI. This is in line with earlier research that suggests employees feel more identified with the company and are more emotionally attached and committed when they believe that decisions, resource allocation, and interpersonal treatment are fair (Colquitt et al., 2001; Olkkonen & Lipponen, 2006). Since workers who identify with their company are more likely to internalize its ideals and form a closer emotional bond, OI is a crucial psychological process that improves the link between OJ and AC (Tyler & Blader, 2003; Van Knippenberg & Sleebos, 2006).

The results of the study confirm H_{11} by demonstrating that OJ influences OCB among NGO personnel through the successive mediating effects of OI and AC. Employees who feel that choices, resource distribution, and interpersonal treatment are fair are more likely to develop a strong sense of connection with the organization, according to previous research. This, in turn, results in a stronger emotional bond and makes them more inclined to make decisions that are advantageous to the business and their colleagues (Colquitt et al., 2001; Tyler & Blader, 2003; Olkkonen & Lipponen, 2006).

6. Conclusion and Future Research Direction

The objective of the research was to find out the affiliation between OJ and OCB with the sequential mediating effect of OI and AC. Based on the study it was found that there was no considerable relationship between OJ and OCB. To give a thorough knowledge of employee commitment in the NGO sector, future study should examine the OJ-OCB. Additionally, the impact of OJ on OCB was examined using the role of AC. It was clear that the mediating impact would not improve the OJ-OBC association since the study did not support the relationship between OJ and AC. According to these findings, nonprofit organizations should focus on factors including inclusive leadership, organizational environment, and work satisfaction in addition to fairness perceptions to increase employees' emotional commitment (Alghofeli et al., 2024; Smith et al., 2018). Future research should look at these additional characteristics to have a more complete understanding of employee devotion in the NGO sector.

However, the results found significant effects on the OJ-OCB and AC-OCB relationships, which emphasize how crucial it is to support OI in NGOs in order to increase staff dedication. Establishing a clear and compelling mission, encouraging inclusive leadership, and improving internal communication to foster a feeling of

purpose are all ways that organizations might do this (Dutton et al., 1994; Bartel, 2001). To increase workers' identification and emotional involvement in the company, organizations should prioritize establishing clear policies, guaranteeing distributive and procedural fairness, and encouraging inclusive leadership (Bartel, 2001; Lipponen et al., 2005).

By enhancing workers' feeling of belonging and bringing their personal values into line with the organization's, OI acts as the initial mediating mechanism (Bartel, 2001; Van Knippenberg & Sleebos, 2006). Higher levels of OCB result from this identification as it encourages AC, which in turn increases employees' willingness to contribute outside of their official job duties (Meyer et al., 2006; Riketta, 2005). According to the findings, business practices have a direct effect on employee behavior in addition to fostering a psychological process that strengthens identification and commitment, which in turn encourages employees to act in a civic manner.

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